

USING GRAPHIC NOVELS AS A MULTIMODAL
TEXT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL
COMPETENCE

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Abstract Lexical competence is important aspect of learning a foreign language. Having lexical competence is closely related to the level of knowledge of a foreign language. Today's world education requires instructors to be creative and organize their lesson more innovative and successful. The application of graphic novels to the teaching process is considered one of the new approaches that has highly effect in vocabulary acquisition. The purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of using graphic novels and examine their role in the development of lexical competence.

Keywords: vocabulary, lexical competence, graphic novel, approach, guessing by picture.

Graphic novels and their characteristics.

Visual aids are the commonly used type of materials in teaching English language. Indeed, visual images: graphs, graphic novels, diagrams, tables and illustrations have become an integral part of foreign language learning materials.

Graphic novels are similar to comic books, an art form that combines images and text to tell a story. Multimodal graphic novels use visuals and text to tell a story. This type of novels contains various modal resources such as image segments, captions, sound effects and written text for a rich and immersive reading experience. In graphic novels, the images tell most of the story. In addition, graphic novels often refer to dialogue and sound effects.

British methodist scholar Stephen Cary points to a rich context for mastering the vocabulary of graphic novels. The combination of visuals and text helps students develop word meanings.

Compared to other genres, graphic novels stand as an art form that incorporates multiple productions. For example, novels speak in writing; and picture books tell a story with text along with illustrations; and film does this with moving images and dialogue. As for graphic novels, they combine all the parts of placement in the above genres in a unique way.

According to Australian researchers S. Murakami and M. Bryce, memory storage can be effectively produced in conjunction with images and verbal speech, rather than loading a verbal or nonverbal product alone. This theory was developed by psychologist, R. Mayer. He argues that people learn new knowledge more deeply with a combination of words and graphics than with words alone. Therefore, the unique balance of visual image and written text in graphic novels helps to increase the literacy of students' lexical knowledge. Graphic, graphic novels are intended for physically young children, but also it is suitable for adults who have various types of learning styles. The most useful thing is that the concise text of the graphic novels combined with pictures help learners to understand easily. Students who are passive and have lack of vocabulary knowledge, feel enjoyed and motivated in English language classroom learning through graphic novels.

Graphic novels and motivation.

The use of graphic novels in the process of vocabulary learning and teaching increases the activity and motivation of students in the lesson. Many pedagogies argue that motivation is an important factor in learning that directly affects student learning. The outcome and motivation of students who learn only from plain text may be much lower than those who use graphic novels. This is because graphic novels include aspects to make learning easier for their readers.

Providing a visual and comfortable environment, with productive resources that combine interactive activities or applying technology and multimedia based

approach help teachers make vocabulary learning more dynamic, interactive and interesting, moreover develop students' lexical competence and motivation.

The methodology of using graphic novels

Graphic novel is one of the authentic materials that is equally useful and enjoyable not only for children, but also for adults. Of course, it is important to determine students' need and interest before choosing learning materials. Because using appropriate materials such as, graphic novels which are suitable for different levels make learning process more effectively and efficiently. Teachers should organize a teaching method that includes various innovative activities to use graphic novel in class. To achieve better result in improving lexical competence, we set a number of techniques as following:

- Familiarize students with the material before introducing the graphic novel to students. In this process, a number of pre-reading activities can be taken away.
- Guessing by Picture activity. In this activity teacher presents some of the pictures related to the book on a big screen. Students should try to think about the content of the book and the role of the characters in it by observing the picture.
- In the reading exercise, the teacher asked the students about the words that were unfamiliar to them. Student should guess the meaning of words with the help of pictures. If students have difficulty with comprehension of words, teacher explains them to students.
- In the next step, students are given worksheet that include a small part of graphic novel. To consolidate new words students should rewrite the passage changing the words into their synonyms.
- At the last step student share their writing with pairs and retell it each other.

By this way learners make progress not only in their lexical competence but also in other four language skills. In conclusion it is worth to emphasize that incorporating graphic novels with curriculum is the most successful way to change dull classroom into engaging and exciting learning place for students.

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